

How to get Fine-tuned (specialized) LLMs for your academic need with de.KCD

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1 hr <https://events.hifis.net/event/2617/>

Why fine-tune?

Fine tune is when you train an LLM like chat GPT for something specific

Fine tune sacrifices general performance for specialized performance

Specialized systems often have fewer patterns that fit in a smaller model

Smaller models are faster and easier to provision.

Specialized systems are more sensitive to noisy data.

If you have clean and specialised data,

Fine-tuning a model will most likely provide better performance

than a general model, even a larger model,

If the data is not publicly available,

it may perform better than a commercially available model.

Where to get help?

Email me miranda@embl.de or contact de.KCD to tell us about your cloud computing needs or for help with cloud storage, even to get training for using cloud technologies. We don't focus on AI, we focus on helping you setup and use systems that run on the web like LLMs, or secure training environments.

I suggest you use LLMs to automate tedious tasks that can enhance your results.

Create LLM agents to permutate over a wide range of options within constraints to find the best options.

The basis for improving the performance of LLMs is validated data, data that has been reviewed and consistent, even better is data that has been corrected! By making this data accessible you can contribute to improving LLMs for yourself and for others. We at de.KCD want to help you make your data (or your model weights) available on the cloud. Your expertise can help others.

Share your **LLM experience** to miranda@embl.de

Outline

- N-shot prompt: using chat with examples
 - Context rot: too much info distracts from the goal
- System Prompt: instructions by the provider not the user of the chat
 - Conflicting pre-train: Training data is not consistent with context
- RAG: search through your dataset for context
 - Can do both: fine-tune and RAG simultaneously
 - Can do better: small fine-tune LLM with good examples, outperform large LLMs
 - Can't do other: Fine-Tune can replace patterns, disable patterns
 - Privacy, etc.: when its free you are the product, your data, your corrections
- Dataset: good quality prompt and response collection
 - Huggingface: everyone can share everything about AI
 - Instructlab: everyone can update one model
 - Your own: given the compute infrastructure, what you do is yours
- Fine-Tune: set a new default behaviour,
 - Beware collapse: replaced patterns don't intertwine
 - Hugging face: using Google Colab notebook
 - Locally: if you have enough hardware
 - Ollama: Command line interface for LLMs
 - Podman AI studio: using docker containers
 - LM studio: GUI interface to LLMs
 - Open WebUI: your Web-app like chatGPT
 - On the cloud: using some other hardware
 - Jupyter notebook: for exploring and investigating
 - Kubernetes: for putting the software on the hardware
 - de.KCD: fo support

A Toy Example:

I want easily get keywords for digital objects, like lab notes or datasets,

I also want to automatically get as much metadata as possible, a few metadata fields are in controlled vocabularies.

Some objects are linked I would like to be notified of those links

- Get my digital object is a video
 - NFDITalk (7 July 2025): NFDI4DS Gateway and Portal
 - But only about: the NFDI4DS portal, and the metadata standard
- Using <https://notebooklm.google.com/> generate a transcript and a mind-map to select the item of interest,
- Request keywords for the digital object: (a word document with notes)
 - In notebooklm....
 - In <https://www.perplexity.ai/>
- I would like the keywords to be more significant, not so many, ask perplexity to generate a prompt to generate a well defined short list of keywords...

n-shot prompting

*Read the provided document and analyze its core topics. Then, generate a concise and well-defined list of 3–7 keywords that best encapsulate the **main concepts, standards, technologies, and applications discussed, avoiding generic words**. The keywords should accurately reflect the essential subject matter and enable effective search or indexing.*

System prompt

- Do key extraction for every document i provide
 - Make a system prompt in <https://chat-ai.academiccloud.de>
 - Compare LLama 8B to 70B, and also Deepseek R1; notice the duration
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Rag

- Upload your files to with <https://chat-ai.academiccloud.de/arcanas/>.
 - Index the files: generate a numeric “concept” of the words in the document
 - Explore code at <https://github.com/haesleinhuepf/simple-rag/blob/main/simple-rag.ipynb>
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Dataset

- Explore <https://huggingface.co/> to find datasets, use the search

- Use <https://instructlab.ai/> to visualize intertwined pattern adaptation
 - Video example, (includes complete example of deploying LLMs)
 - ▶ **Generative AI Development with Podman AI Lab, InstructLab, & OpenShift AI**
 - *From a small set of questions and answers generate a large set to use for fine-tuning*
 - Use [this notebook](#) to generate questions and answers from documents, for fine tuning
 - More about [fine-tuning](#)
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Fine Tuning

- Explore a [medical base model](#) and use auto train to fine tune
 - More [auto train modes](#)
 - Try second part of [this notebook](#) and [more about fine tuning](#)
 - Run the [Scads.ai tutorial notebook](#) (thanks Dr. Robert Haase) on your infrastructure
 - Email miranda@embl.de and ask for a jupyter notebook infrastructure to run the tutorial
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<https://helmholtz.cloud/> “ train AI models,”

How can we help you use cloud computing and cloud storage?
Would you like training to use the cloud

site: <https://datenkompetenz.cloud>

contact: info@datenkompetenz.cloud

chat: [#dekcd:uni-bielefeld.de](#)